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of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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The Cycle of Service

Serving meals you can't even pronounce,
some you've never even tried
yet you're expected to sell them with a smile.

Even when you're not okay,
you still have to look okay.
Because in hospitality, emotions are part of the job.

From greeting guests to taking orders,
serving food, drinks, and patience
you make sure everything feels perfect.

When one table leaves, another comes.
Same smile, same effort, same care.
That's emotional labor.
That's hospitality.